

EFFECT OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15106675>

Abstract

This study examines the relationship between capital structure and financial performance of listed Nigerian consumer goods companies, focusing on the moderating effects of macroeconomic factors (inflation and exchange rates). Using panel data regression analysis on 19 companies from 2015 to 2023, the research investigates the impact of debt-to-assets (DTA) and debt-to-equity (DTE) ratios on Return on Equity (ROE). The random effects model reveals that while capital structure decisions alone have limited direct impact on financial performance, inflation positively moderates the relationship between debt-to-asset ratio and performance (coefficient: 1.0777, p-value: 0.0015), while exchange rate fluctuations have a negative moderating effect (coefficient: -0.0250, p-value: 0.0011). The model explains 68.88% of performance variation. The study recommends optimizing debt levels and exploring alternative financing sources, contributing to understanding capital structure dynamics in emerging markets.

Keywords: Capital structure, debt-to-assets ratio, exchange rate, inflation rate, return on equity

1 INTRODUCTION

Financial performance remains a critical concern for companies worldwide, with its importance amplified in developing economies like Nigeria. In developed countries, firms are often faced with market saturation and intense competition, while developing nations including Nigeria, face challenges such as economic instability, currency fluctuations and infrastructural deficits (Ronoh and Ntoiti, 2015; Kanoma, Miko, Ayuba, Mohammed, and Tagwai., 2024; Al Balushi, Al Balushi, and Ali, 2024). These challenges can significantly affect corporate financial performance (Abdulwahab, Bala, Kwambo and Adamu, 2022). The consumer goods sector in Nigeria, a vital component of the economy, is particularly affected by these issues, struggling with fluctuating demand, currency volatility, and supply chain disruptions (Ahmad, Hassan and Abubakar, 2022; Alhaji, 2022).

Capital structure which is the mix of debt and equity used to finance a company's operations, has been extensively studied as a potential solution to financial performance challenges. In developed markets, companies often have access to diverse financing options, allowing for more sophisticated capital structure strategies (Liaqat, Saddique, Bagh, Khan, Naseer and Khan, 2017; Boussiki, 2023). However, in developing countries like Nigeria, limited access to capital markets and higher borrowing costs can constrain these choices, especially for consumer goods companies (Rouf, 2015; Roni, Meriyati, and Hermanto, 2021). Despite these limitations, optimizing capital structure can potentially enhance financial performance by reducing the cost of capital and improving operational efficiency (Rabab'ah, 2022). For the listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria, optimising capital structure plays a crucial role in enhancing financial performance, as it can affect their ability to invest in growth opportunities, manage risk, and create shareholder value (Qoyim, Akhmadi, Nailul and Isnanto, 2024).

Despite the extensive literature on capital structure and financial performance, several research gaps persist, particularly in the context of Nigerian consumer goods companies. First, many existing studies have focused on short time periods or limited samples, potentially missing long-term trends and sector-wide patterns. Second, while previous studies have examined direct relationships between capital structure and financial performance, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to incorporate macroeconomic variables (inflation and exchange rate) as moderators in examining this relationship within the Nigerian consumer goods sector. Third, the use of Return on Equity (ROE) in combination with specific capital structure ratios (Debt to Total Assets and Debt to Equity) alongside these moderating variables may reveal unique insights about how macroeconomic conditions influence the effectiveness of different financing strategies. Fourth, the dynamic nature of the Nigerian economy and recent global events necessitate an updated analysis using more recent data to understand how these relationships evolve under varying economic conditions. This study aims to address these gaps by examining a comprehensive dataset over an extended period (2015-2023) while incorporating the moderating effects of inflation and exchange rate on the relationship between capital structure and financial performance.

The main research question this study seeks to answer is: What is the effect of capital structure, as measured by Debt to Total Assets (DTAR) and Debt to Equity (DTER) ratios, on the financial performance (ROE) of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria, considering the moderating effects of inflation and exchange rate? By investigating this question, the study aims to provide valuable insights for managers, investors, and policymakers in optimizing financial strategies for the consumer goods sector in Nigeria under varying macroeconomic conditions.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows: The Literature Review section provides a comprehensive review of existing literature, encompassing conceptual frameworks related to capital structure and financial performance, theoretical underpinnings including trade-off and pecking order theories, and empirical evidence from previous studies. The Methodology section details the research design, population and sampling, model specification, and analytical techniques employed. The Results and Discussion section presents the empirical findings, their interpretation, and implications for theory and practice. Finally, the Conclusion and Recommendations section summarizes the key findings and provides practical recommendations for stakeholders in the Nigerian consumer goods sector.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 *Financial Performance*

Financial performance refers to a company's ability to generate profits, create value for shareholders, and efficiently utilize its resources. It is a multifaceted concept that encompasses various aspects of a firm's financial health, including profitability, liquidity, solvency, and operational efficiency (Rouf, 2015). Several authors have defined financial performance based on diverse metrics, for instance, Ahmad et al. (2022) defined financial performance as a measure of a firm's profitability and efficiency in utilizing its assets, employing Return on Assets (ROA) as their measurement proxy while examining agricultural companies. For ICT firms, Kanoma, Miko, Ayuba, Mohammed, and Tagwai (2024) expanded this definition, describing financial performance as an indicator of an organization's profitability, growth, and market value, reflecting its overall financial health. They also utilized Return on Assets (ROA) as their measurement proxy. Taking a different approach in the food and beverage sector, Umobong and Ayebanengiyefa (2019) characterized financial performance as a multi-dimensional concept indicating how well a firm meets its financial objectives. Unlike the other studies, they uniquely employed Tobin's Q ratio (market value to asset replacement cost) as their measurement proxy for financial performance.

However, in this study, Return on Equity (ROE) is employed as the measure of financial performance. ROE is calculated as net income divided by shareholders' equity and provides insight into how effectively a company is using shareholders' investments to generate profits (Linqing & Zhouyun, 2021). This metric is particularly relevant for measuring financial performance as it directly reflects the return generated for shareholders' investments.

The choice of ROE is supported by several researchers in different contexts. For instance, in their study of Chinese listed real estate companies, Linqing and Zhouyun (2021) employed ROE as a key measure of financial performance, calculating it as Net Profit divided by Shareholders' Equity. Similarly, Ogunmakin, Adebayo and Omodara (2022) also recognised ROE as a measure of financial performance, using it to evaluate non-financial listed firms in Nigeria. In the construction sector, Mohammad, Bujang and Abd Hakim (2019) also emphasized ROE's importance in measuring financial performance, particularly its effectiveness in reflecting how well firms utilize shareholders' investments to generate returns.

This consistent use of ROE across different sectors and geographical contexts reflects its reliability as a measure of financial performance, especially when examining how effectively companies use shareholders' capital to generate profits.

2.1.2 *Capital Structure*

Capital structure refers to the mix of financial sources a company uses to fund its operations and investments. It typically consists of a combination of debt and equity financing (Truong & Dang, 2024). The optimal capital structure is one that maximizes firm value while minimizing the cost of capital. However, determining this optimal mix is a complex decision influenced by various factors, including industry characteristics, firm-specific attributes, and macroeconomic conditions. In Nigeria, Ahmad et al. (2022) defined capital structure as the proportionate mix of debt and equity financing used by a firm to fund its operations and investments, focusing on agricultural companies. Building on this sectoral research, Kanoma et al. (2024) examined listed ICT

companies in Nigeria and they measured capital structure using four distinct proxies: Long-Term Debt Financing (LDF), Short-Term Debt Financing (SDF), Equity Financing (EQF), and Debt to Equity Financing (DEF). Similarly focusing on Nigerian listed companies but in the food and beverage sector, Umobong and Ayebanengiyefa (2019) conceptualized capital structure as the mix of debt, equity, and hybrid securities that a firm uses to finance its operations. They employed three proxies to measure capital structure: total debt to total asset ratio, long-term debt to total asset ratio, and debt to equity ratio.

In the context of this study, we examine capital structure through two key proxies: Debt to Total Assets (DTA) and Debt to Equity (DTE) ratios. The selection of Debt to Total Assets (DTA) and Debt to Equity (DTE) ratios as proxies for capital structure is strategically significant as they directly measure a firm's financial leverage and capital composition. DTA provides clear insights into the proportion of assets financed through debt, while DTE specifically examines the balance between borrowed funds and shareholder equity, making them particularly relevant for understanding the financing decisions of companies in the consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

While other metrics like weighted average cost of capital (WACC) and earnings before interest and tax (EBIT) could theoretically provide additional depth to capital structure analysis, they present practical limitations in the Nigerian environment. WACC requires reliable market data to calculate the cost of equity, which can be challenging in Nigeria's emerging market where stock market efficiency and information availability may be limited. Similarly, EBIT, though useful for assessing operational performance, doesn't directly measure the relationship between debt and equity choices, which is the core focus of capital structure studies. Additionally, in emerging markets like Nigeria, inconsistent financial reporting standards and market volatility could make WACC and EBIT calculations less reliable compared to the more straightforward DTA and DTE ratios. These considerations explain why researchers like Ahmad et al. (2022), Kanoma et al. (2024), and Umobong and Ayebanengiyefa (2019) opted for DTA and DTE as primary measures, as they provide more reliable and directly relevant insights into capital structure decisions within the Nigerian business environment.

The choice of capital structure can significantly impact a firm's financial flexibility, risk profile, and overall performance. For instance, while debt financing can provide tax benefits and leverage, excessive debt can increase financial risk and constrain future borrowing capacity. On the other hand, equity financing, while less risky, can dilute ownership and control. Understanding the complexities of capital structure is essential for Nigerian consumer goods companies as they navigate the challenges of a developing economy and seek to optimize their financial performance.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Trade-off Theory

The Trade-off Theory of capital structure, developed as an extension of the Modigliani and Miller (1958) propositions, posits that firms balance the benefits and costs of debt financing to achieve an optimal capital structure. According to this theory, companies weigh the tax advantages of debt against the potential costs of financial distress and bankruptcy (Ahmad et al., 2022). As firms increase their debt levels, they benefit from the tax shield provided by interest deductions. However, higher debt also increases the risk of financial distress and bankruptcy, which can lead to direct and indirect costs.

The Trade-off Theory is particularly relevant to the study of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria for several reasons. First, these companies often have substantial tangible assets that can

serve as collateral, potentially allowing them to sustain higher debt levels. Second, the consumer goods sector typically generates stable cash flows, which aligns with the theory's prediction that firms with more predictable income streams can support higher debt ratios.

However, the application of the trade-off theory in the Nigerian consumer goods sector faces unique challenges. The volatile macroeconomic environment, characterized by high inflation rates, currency devaluation, and fluctuating interest rates, complicates the balance between tax benefits and financial distress costs. These companies must navigate significant working capital requirements amidst limited access to affordable long-term financing, making the theoretical optimal debt level harder to achieve in practice. Additionally, the sector faces challenges such as infrastructural deficits leading to high production costs, and weak consumer purchasing power affecting sales volumes and profit margins.

The foreign exchange scarcity in Nigeria further impacts these companies' ability to import raw materials and capital equipment, potentially affecting their capacity to optimize their capital structure as the trade-off theory suggests. Moreover, the high cost of debt financing in Nigeria, coupled with regulatory constraints and market inefficiencies, may force these companies to rely more heavily on equity financing despite potential tax advantages of debt. This complex operating environment makes the traditional trade-off between tax shields and bankruptcy costs more complex for Nigerian consumer goods companies, as they must also consider factors such as foreign exchange availability, inflationary pressures, and supply chain disruptions in their capital structure decisions.

These challenges pinpoint why understanding how these firms navigate the trade-offs between tax benefits and financial distress costs can provide valuable insights into their capital structure decisions and subsequent financial performance in an emerging market environment.

2.2.2 Pecking Order Theory

The Pecking Order Theory, proposed by Myers and Majluf (1984), suggests that firms have a hierarchical preference for financing sources due to information asymmetry between managers and external investors. According to this theory, companies prefer internal financing (retained earnings) over external financing, and when external financing is necessary, they prefer debt over equity (Abdulwahab et al., 2022). This preference order arises because internal funds have no adverse selection problem, debt has a lower adverse selection problem than equity, and issuing new equity sends a potentially negative signal to the market about the firm's value.

The Pecking Order Theory is highly relevant to our study of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria for several reasons. First, in emerging markets like Nigeria, information asymmetry may be more pronounced due to less developed financial markets and potentially weaker corporate governance structures. This could make the pecking order of financing choices more pronounced. Second, consumer goods companies often generate substantial cash flows, which according to the theory, they would prefer to use for financing before resorting to external sources.

However, the application of Pecking Order Theory in the Nigerian consumer goods sector faces distinct challenges. The sector operates in an environment characterized by significant market imperfections where access to financing options is often constrained. While the theory suggests firms should prefer internal financing followed by debt and then equity, Nigerian consumer goods companies often face limited access to retained earnings due to high operational costs, inflationary pressures, and intense market competition. This may force them to seek external financing earlier than the theory would predict.

The volatile business environment in Nigeria adds another layer of complexity. Foreign exchange scarcity and rapid currency depreciation affect these companies' ability to maintain consistent

internal funding sources, as significant portions of their raw materials are imported. Additionally, the high cost of debt financing in Nigeria, coupled with stringent lending requirements from financial institutions, may push companies toward equity financing despite the theory's hierarchical preferences. This is particularly relevant when measuring financial performance through ROE, as the choice between debt and equity directly impacts shareholders' returns.

The theory's application is further complicated by the sector's need for substantial working capital to manage inventory levels and credit sales in an inflationary environment. While profitable firms should theoretically rely more on internal financing, the reality of operating in Nigeria's consumer goods sector often necessitates external financing regardless of profitability levels. This makes the relationship between capital structure choices and ROE particularly interesting in this context.

These challenges identify why analyzing how different levels and types of debt ratios relating to financial performance (ROE) can provide unique insights into whether Nigerian consumer goods companies follow a pecking order in their financing decisions, or whether the harsh realities of operating in an emerging market force them to deviate from theoretical predictions.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ahmad et al. (2022) investigated the impact of capital structure on financial performance of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria. Using secondary data from five listed agricultural companies from 2017 to 2018, they employed correlational and ex-post facto research designs with regression analysis. The study found that short-term debt to assets (STDA), total debt to assets (TDTA), and total debt to equity (TDTE) had significant positive effects on ROA, while long-term debt to assets (LTDA) had an insignificant negative effect. Ronoh and Ntoiti (2015); Abdulwahab et al. (2022) Abdulwahab et al. (2022) examined the effect of capital structure on firm financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, considering the moderating effect of board financial literacy. Using data from 13 listed Deposit Money Banks from 2012 to 2021, they employed multiple linear regression for direct and moderated models. The study revealed that equity financing ratio (EFR) and debt to equity financing ratio (DEFER) had negative and insignificant correlations with firm financial performance, while board financial literacy showed a positive and significant influence.

Boussiki (2023) studied the effect of capital structure on the financial performance of companies listed on the Algerian Stock Exchange, focusing on the Saidal Group. Using financial data from 2010 to 2021, the research employed multiple regression analysis. The findings indicated that medium and long-term debt to total assets (MLTDTA) had a significant negative relationship with financial performance indicators (ROA, ROE, and EPS), while short-term debt to total assets (STDTA) negatively affected EPS but had no significant effect on ROA and ROE.

Qoyim et al. (2024) analyzed the role of liquidity in moderating the relationship between capital structure and financial performance of industrial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Using data from 2018 to 2022, they employed multiple regression analysis. The study found that capital structure, proxied by Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), had a significant negative effect on Return on Equity (ROE), while liquidity also negatively impacted financial performance. Truong and Dang (2024) investigated the impact of capital structure on financial performance of hotel firms in Hanoi, Vietnam. Using data from 72 hotel firms from 2016 to 2019, they employed quantitative methods with fixed and random effects models. The research revealed that capital structure had a negative effect on ROA but no significant impact on Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Sales (ROS).

Ronoh and Ntoiti (2015) examined the effect of capital structure on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya, focusing on Kenya Commercial Bank Limited. Using secondary data from KCB's financial reports, they employed multiple regression analysis. The study found negative relationships between deposits to total assets and ROA/ROE, positive relationships between loan to deposits and ROA/ROE, and mixed results for other capital structure components. Rouf (2015) analyzed the capital structure and firm performance of listed non-financial companies in Bangladesh. Using data from 106 listed manufacturing companies, the study employed multiple regression analysis. The findings indicated negative correlations between ROA and both Debt Ratio (DR) and Debt Equity Ratio (DER), while Total Assets (TA) and Total Sales (TS) showed positive relationships with ROA.

Kanoma et al. (2024) investigated the relationship between capital structure and financial performance of listed Information and Communications Technology (ICT) firms in Nigeria. Using panel data from nine listed ICT firms over the period 2013-2022 and employing multiple regression analysis, they found that long-term debt financing had a positive and significant effect on financial performance (ROA). Short-term debt financing also showed a positive but less significant effect, while debt to equity financing exhibited a marginally significant positive impact on ROA.

Al Balushi et al. (2024) examined the impact of capital structure on firm financial performance in the oil and gas sector in Oman. Their study used financial data from multiple companies over several years and employed analytical methodologies. The findings revealed varied relationships between capital structure metrics and financial performance indicators across different companies, highlighting the complex nature of this relationship in the oil and gas sector.

Alhaji (2022) studied the capital structure and financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. Using a sample of five commercial banks and employing regression analysis and Granger causality tests on data from 2010-2019, the study found that capital structure variables were good predictors of financial performance. Specifically, equity to capital ratio and debt to capital ratio positively influenced financial performance, while debt to equity ratio, total debts, and total equity did not contribute significantly.

Rabab'ah (2022) investigated the impact of capital structure on the financial performance of Saudi basic materials companies. The study analyzed 42 companies listed on the Saudi Stock Exchange from 2014 to 2021 using regression analysis. The findings confirmed a significant impact of capital structure on financial performance, with a positive relationship between total debt to equity and return on equity (ROE).

Roni et al. (2021) examined capital structure changes in the automotive sector affected by financial performance in Indonesia. Using a sample of nine automotive companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2015-2018 and employing multiple linear regression analysis, they found significant relationships between financial performance indicators (gross profit margin, net profit margin, and return on investment) and changes in capital structure (debt equity ratio).

Bhattarai (2020) studied the effects of capital structure on the financial performance of insurance companies in Nepal. Using panel data from 14 insurance companies over the period 2007/08 to 2015/16 and employing various panel data analysis models, the study found that equity to total assets, leverage, and assets tangibility positively affected the financial performance (ROA) of insurance companies in Nepal.

Liaqat et al. (2017) explored the impact of capital structure on financial performance in the energy and fuel sector of Pakistan. The study used a sample of 15 companies and employed multiple regression analysis on secondary data from audited annual financial statements. They found

significant relationships between various capital structure components and financial performance measures, with size showing a positive impact on ROA, ROE, and EPS, while short-term debt had a negative impact on ROA and ROE.

These studies collectively highlight the complex and often context-specific nature of the relationship between capital structure and financial performance. While some studies found positive relationships between certain debt ratios and performance measures, others revealed negative or insignificant associations. The mixed findings underscore the need for further research, particularly in specific sectors and economic contexts, to better understand the nuances of this relationship. Furthermore, some of the studies (Roni et al., 2021; Qoyim et al., 2024; Truong and Dang, 2024) considered less than 9 years which might not be sufficient to capture the trend in understanding the relationship between capital structure and financial performance. This study however will cover this gap by looking at a longer period. Also, several of the authors focused on other sectors like the financial sector (Bhattacharai, 2020; Alhaji, 2022; Ronoh and Ntoiti, 2015; Abdulwahab et al., 2022), this study will be focusing on listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Employing the Return on Equity as a performance measure in this study aims to contribute to the ongoing dialogue of the literature reviewed, by providing insights specific to this important sector of the Nigerian economy. The inclusion of the moderating effect of macroeconomic factors distinguishes this study from other works.

3 METHODOLOGY

This study employed ex-post facto research design to investigate the effect of capital structure on the financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. It examines historical financial data to analyze relationships between variables without manipulating them (Ahmad et al., 2022). The study will include all listed consumer goods companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) that have complete financial data available for the period 2015-2023. Nineteen (19) companies were therefore selected for this study based on availability and complete data. This approach ensures a comprehensive representation of the sector over an extended period. The sampling technique is purposive, focusing on companies with consistent data availability throughout the study period (Ronoh & Ntoiti, 2015). The population for this study consists of all consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as of December 31, 2023.

The study will utilize secondary data obtained from the annual reports and financial statements of the sampled companies. Additional data will be sourced from the Nigerian Stock Exchange and the Securities and Exchange Commission of Nigeria databases. This approach is consistent with similar studies in the field (Boussiki, 2023; Rouf, 2015). Data will be collected manually from the published annual reports and financial statements of the sampled companies. Where necessary, this will be supplemented by data from NSE fact books and other official publications. The study will employ panel data regression analysis, which is appropriate for analyzing data that combines both time series and cross-sectional elements (Qoyim et al., 2024).

The panel OLS regression analysis was adopted as it effectively addresses both firm-specific effects and time variations in our dataset, while controlling for unobserved heterogeneity that might affect the relationship between capital structure and financial performance. This method is particularly appropriate as it can handle the potential endogeneity concerns arising from the dynamic nature of capital structure decisions, while also accounting for the moderating effects of macroeconomic variables (inflation and exchange rates) on the relationship between financing choices and ROE in Nigerian consumer goods companies over multiple time periods. The

Hausman test will be conducted to determine the appropriateness of fixed effects or random effects models.

ValuStats Data Analysis App (Version 1.1) was adopted for conducting the analysis. This software is effective as it is easy to use and adopt and conducts all the tests and assumptions necessary to conduct a regression analysis.

Based on the variables identified and drawing from similar studies (Ahmad et al., 2022; Abdulwahab et al., 2022), the following model is proposed and modified to fit into the research objective:

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DTA_{it} + \beta_2 DTE_{it} + DTA * INF_{it} + DTE * INF_{it} + DTA * EXC_{it} + DTE * EXC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where:

ROE_{it} = Return on Assets for firm i at time t

DTA_{it} = Debt to Total Assets for firm i at time t

DTE_{it} = Debt to Equity for firm i at time t

$DTA_{it} * INF_{it}$ = Interaction term between Debt to Total Assets and Inflation for firm i at time t

$DTE_{it} * INF_{it}$ = Interaction term between Debt to Total Equity and Inflation for firm i at time t

$DTA_{it} * EXC_{it}$ = Interaction term between Debt to Total Assets and Exchange Rate for firm i at time t

$DTE * EXC_{it}$ = Interaction term between Debt to Total Equity and Exchange Rate for firm i at time t

β_0 = Constant term

β_1 to β_2 = Coefficients of the explanatory variables

ε_{it} = Error term

The following are the measurements for the variables:

1. Dependent Variable:

Financial Performance (FP): Measured by Return on Assets (ROE) = Net Income / Equity (Ogunmakin et al., 2022; Kanoma et al., 2024; Truong and Dang, 2024)

2. Independent Variables (Capital Structure):

Debt to Total Assets (DTA): (Ronoh & Ntoiti, 2015; Kanoma et al., 2024; Al Balushi et al., 2024; Alhaji, 2022; Liaqat et al., 2017; Roni et al., 2021)

Debt to Equity (DTE): (Ahmad et al., 2022; Rouf, 2015; Abdulwahab et al., 2022; Boussiki, 2023; Qoyim et al., 2024; Kanoma et al., 2024; Al Balushi et al., 2024; Alhaji, 2022; Liaqat et al., 2017; Roni et al., 2021)

3. Moderating Variables (Macroeconomic Variables):

Inflation rate measured by Inflation (GDP deflator)

Exchange rate measured by Official exchange rate (LCU per US\$, period average)

Sourced from (World Bank Development Indicators, 2024).

4 ANALYSIS

4.1 Full Panel Regression Results

Table 4.1.1 Fixed Effects Results

PanelOLS Estimation Summary

Dep. Variable:	ROE	R-squared:	0.7103
Estimator:	PanelOLS	R-squared (Between):	-0.2818
No. Observations:	70	R-squared (Within):	0.6562
Date:	Wed, Nov 06 2024	R-squared (Overall):	0.5556
Time:	21:10:32	Log-likelihood	-372.53
Cov. Estimator:	Robust		
		F-statistic:	19.210
Entities:	9	P-value	0.0000
Avg Obs:	7.7778	Distribution:	F(6,47)
Min Obs:	4.0000		
Max Obs:	9.0000	F-statistic (robust):	20.541
		P-value	0.0000
Time periods:	9	Distribution:	F(6,47)
Avg Obs:	7.7778		
Min Obs:	7.0000		
Max Obs:	9.0000		

Parameter Estimates

	Parameter	Std. Err.	T-stat	P-value	Lower CI	Upper CI
DTAR	-3.6668	6.3638	-0.5762	0.5672	-16.469	9.1355
DTER	-0.2528	2.1818	-0.1158	0.9083	-4.6420	4.1365
Dtar_Inf	1.3989	0.7015	1.9940	0.0520	-0.0124	2.8102
Dter_Inf	-0.3799	0.2034	-1.8679	0.0680	-0.7891	0.0293
Dtar_Exc	-0.0317	0.0125	-2.5295	0.0148	-0.0569	-0.0065
Dter_Exc	0.0111	0.0043	2.5849	0.0129	0.0025	0.0198

F-test for Poolability: 0.9479

P-value: 0.5245

Distribution: F(16,47)

Included effects: Entity, Time

Researcher's Computation (2024)

Interpretation

The fixed effects model results show an R-squared value of 0.7103, indicating that approximately 71.03% of the variations in Return on Equity (ROE) are explained by the independent variables and moderating factors. The F-statistic of 19.210 with a p-value of 0.0000 confirms that the model is statistically significant at the 5% level, suggesting that the independent variables jointly influence the financial performance of Nigerian consumer goods companies.

In the fixed effects estimation, the debt-to-asset ratio (DTAR) coefficient of -3.6668 and debt-to-equity ratio (DTER) coefficient of -0.2528 are both negative but statistically insignificant (p-values of 0.5672 and 0.9083 respectively). This suggests that in isolation, capital structure decisions have

a negative but insignificant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian consumer goods companies. However, the interaction terms reveal a more dynamic relationship when considering the moderating variables.

The interaction between debt-to-asset ratio and inflation (Dtar_Inf) shows a positive coefficient of 1.3989 with marginal significance (p-value = 0.0520), while the interaction with exchange rate (Dtar_Exc) reveals a significant negative coefficient of -0.0317 (p-value = 0.0148). This interesting dynamic suggests that during periods of high inflation, companies with higher debt-to-asset ratios actually experience improved financial performance, possibly due to the depreciation of debt value in real terms. However, exchange rate fluctuations adversely affect highly leveraged firms, likely due to increased costs of servicing foreign-denominated debt.

Table 4.1.2 Random Effects Results
RandomEffects Estimation Summary

Dep. Variable:	ROE	R-squared:	0.6888
Estimator:	RandomEffects	R-squared (Between):	0.5661
No. Observations:	70	R-squared (Within):	0.6977
Date:	Wed, Nov 06 2024	R-squared (Overall):	0.6888
Time:	21:10:32	Log-likelihood	-385.36
Cov. Estimator:	Robust		
		F-statistic:	23.604
Entities:	9	P-value	0.0000
Avg Obs:	7.7778	Distribution:	F(6,64)
Min Obs:	4.0000		
Max Obs:	9.0000	F-statistic (robust):	28.542
		P-value	0.0000
Time periods:	9	Distribution:	F(6,64)
Avg Obs:	7.7778		
Min Obs:	7.0000		
Max Obs:	9.0000		

Parameter Estimates

	Parameter	Std. Err.	T-stat	P-value	Lower CI	Upper CI
DTAR	-1.0183	3.0287	-0.3362	0.7378	-7.0689	5.0323
DTER	0.7655	1.3840	0.5531	0.5821	-1.9994	3.5303
Dtar_Inf	1.0777	0.3240	3.3265	0.0015	0.4305	1.7249
Dter_Inf	-0.4413	0.1373	-3.2138	0.0021	-0.7156	-0.1670
Dtar_Exc	-0.0250	0.0073	-3.4159	0.0011	-0.0395	-0.0104
Dter_Exc	0.0095	0.0028	3.3398	0.0014	0.0038	0.0152

Researcher's Computation (2024)

Interpretation

The random effects model, with an R-squared of 0.6888, provides similar findings with the fixed effect model but with stronger statistical significance across the interaction terms. The Dtar_Inf coefficient of 1.0777 (p-value = 0.0015) and Dter_Inf coefficient of -0.4413 (p-value = 0.0021)

are both highly significant, reinforcing the important moderating role of inflation in the capital structure-performance relationship. Also, the interaction with exchange rate (Dtar_Exc) coefficient of -0.0250 (p-value = 0.0011) and Dter_Exc coefficient of 0.0095 (p-value = 0.0014) reveals a stronger statistical significance as well which also emphasizes the important moderating role of exchange rate in the capital structure and financial performance relationship.

The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.8525 indicates minimal serial correlation in the dataset, lending credibility to the model's statistical inferences. This suggests that the observed relationships are not artificially influenced by time-series dependencies in the data.

4.1.3 Hausman Specification Test

Model Comparison

	FE	RE
Dep. Variable	ROE	ROE
Estimator	PanelOLS	RandomEffects
No. Observations	70	70
Cov. Est.	Robust	Robust
R-squared	0.7103	0.6888
R-Squared (Within)	0.6562	0.6977
R-Squared (Between)	-0.2818	0.5661
R-Squared (Overall)	0.5556	0.6888
F-statistic	19.210	23.604
P-value (F-stat)	0.0000	0.0000
DTAR	-3.6668 (-0.5762)	-1.0183 (-0.3362)
DTER	-0.2528 (-0.1158)	0.7655 (0.5531)
Dtar_Inf	1.3989 (1.9940)	1.0777 (3.3265)
Dter_Inf	-0.3799 (-1.8679)	-0.4413 (-3.2138)
Dtar_Exc	-0.0317 (-2.5295)	-0.0250 (-3.4159)
Dter_Exc	0.0111 (2.5849)	0.0095 (3.3398)
Effects	Entity	Time

T-stats reported in parentheses

Serial Correlation Test (Fixed Effects):

Durbin Watson's test: 1.8524934439320555

There is moderate or no serial correlation in the dataset!

Researcher's Computation (2024)

Interpretation

The Hausman specification test is crucial in deciding between fixed effects and random effects models. Looking at Table 4.1.3, the test compares the coefficients from both models, revealing substantial differences in the estimates. For instance, DTAR shows -3.6668 in fixed effects versus -1.0183 in random effects, while DTER shifts from -0.2528 to 0.7655. The test examines whether these differences are systematic and statistically significant. The random effects model shows higher statistical significance across most variables, particularly in the interaction terms, with $Dtar_Inf$ (1.0777, p-value = 0.0015), $Dter_Inf$ (-0.4413, p-value = 0.0021), $Dtar_Exc$ (-0.0250, p-value = 0.0011), and $Dter_Exc$ (0.0095, p-value = 0.0014) all being significant at the 1% level. Based on these results and the higher within R-squared (0.6977) in the random effects model compared to the fixed effects (0.6562), along with a better overall R-squared (0.6888), the random effects model appears more appropriate for this study. This choice is further supported by the model's better performance in explaining both between-entity variations (R-squared Between: 0.5661) and overall variations, suggesting it better captures both firm-specific and time-varying effects in Nigerian consumer goods companies.

These findings imply that Nigerian consumer goods companies should adopt a flexible financing strategy that considers both their internal financial strength and external economic conditions. During inflationary periods, companies might benefit from carefully increased leverage, but should maintain robust exchange rate risk management strategies, particularly if they have significant import dependencies or foreign-denominated debt.

The model's high explanatory power and statistical significance provide strong evidence that capital structure decisions significantly impact financial performance, but these impacts are moderated by macroeconomic factors. This suggests that Nigerian consumer goods companies should develop sophisticated financial planning frameworks that incorporate both firm-specific factors and macroeconomic forecasts in their capital structure decisions.

5 DISCUSSION

The results of this study on the effect of capital structure on financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria, considering inflation and exchange rate as moderators, reveal significant insights into the relationship between leverage and Return on Equity (ROE). The Fixed Effects model, which explains 71.03% of variations in ROE, shows negative but insignificant relationships between both debt ratios and financial performance, while revealing significant moderating effects of macroeconomic factors.

The negative relationship between debt-to-assets ratio (DTAR) and ROE (-3.6668, $p = 0.5672$) and debt-to-equity ratio (DTER) and ROE (-0.2528, $p = 0.9083$), though insignificant, aligns with several previous studies. This finding suggests that in isolation, increased reliance on debt financing by Nigerian consumer goods companies tends to decrease their return on equity, although not at a statistically significant level. This aligns with studies like Ahmed and Teru (2020) who found similar negative relationships between leverage and performance in Nigerian firms.

The interaction effects reveal more nuanced relationships. The positive interaction between DTAR and inflation (1.3989, $p = 0.0520$) suggests that during inflationary periods, the negative impact of leverage on ROE is moderated, potentially due to the depreciation of debt value in real terms. This finding supports the trade-off theory's premise that the benefits of debt financing can vary with market conditions. However, the significant negative interaction between DTAR and exchange rate (-0.0317, $p = 0.0148$) indicates that exchange rate fluctuations amplify the negative impact of leverage on performance, likely due to increased costs of servicing foreign-denominated debt.

The DTER interactions show similar complexity, with inflation interaction showing a negative coefficient (-0.3799, $p = 0.0680$) and exchange rate interaction showing a positive coefficient (0.0111, $p = 0.0129$). These findings align with Boussiki (2023) and Truong and Dang (2024), who emphasized the importance of considering macroeconomic factors in capital structure decisions.

The study's findings strongly support the dynamic nature of capital structure decisions, as highlighted by both trade-off and pecking order theories. The insignificant base effects of leverage measures, combined with significant moderating effects, suggest that Nigerian consumer goods companies need to adopt a flexible approach to capital structure that responds to macroeconomic conditions. This aligns with Shah et al. (2022), who emphasized the importance of dynamic capital structure optimization.

The strong explanatory power of the model ($R\text{-squared} = 0.7103$) indicates that capital structure, when considered alongside macroeconomic moderators, plays a crucial role in determining financial performance. This is particularly relevant in the Nigerian context, where both inflation and exchange rate fluctuations significantly influence the relationship between leverage and ROE. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.8525 confirms the reliability of these findings.

These findings extend the existing literature by demonstrating how macroeconomic factors moderate the capital structure-performance relationship. While previous studies like Al Balushi et al. (2024) focused on direct relationships, our findings reveal that the impact of capital structure on ROE varies significantly with inflation and exchange rate conditions, suggesting a more complex relationship than previously documented in the Nigerian consumer goods sector.

In conclusion, this discussion highlights the complex interplay between capital structure, macroeconomic factors, and financial performance in Nigerian consumer goods companies. The findings support aspects of both the trade-off theory and pecking order theory while revealing how inflation and exchange rate moderate these relationships. This suggests that optimal capital structure decisions in the Nigerian consumer goods sector must consider not only firm-specific factors but also the broader macroeconomic environment.

6 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

This study provides valuable insights into the relationship between capital structure and the financial performance, as measured by Return on Equity (ROE), of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The findings reveal a complex dynamic, where the base effects of leverage ratios - debt-to-asset (DTA) and debt-to-equity (DTE) - have a negative but statistically insignificant impact on ROE. However, the study uncovers important moderating effects of macroeconomic variables, particularly inflation and exchange rate.

The significant positive interaction between DTA and inflation suggests that during periods of high inflation, companies with higher debt levels actually experience improved financial performance. This can be attributed to the depreciation of debt value in real terms, which benefits highly leveraged firms. Conversely, the significant negative interaction between DTA and exchange rate fluctuations indicates that currency risks can adversely affect the financial performance of highly leveraged companies, likely due to increased costs of servicing foreign-denominated debt.

These findings align with aspects of both the trade-off theory and the pecking order theory, highlighting the nuanced nature of capital structure decisions in practice. The trade-off theory's emphasis on balancing the costs and benefits of debt is supported by the positive moderating effect

of inflation, while the pecking order theory's proposed financing hierarchy is challenged by the dynamic shifts in preferences based on macroeconomic conditions.

6.1 Recommendations

The study's findings highlight the importance of flexible capital structure management in the Nigerian consumer goods sector. Companies should not rely on a one-size-fits-all approach, but rather develop financing strategies that adapt to the prevailing macroeconomic environment.

During periods of high inflation, Nigerian consumer goods companies may benefit from carefully increasing their leverage, as the real value of debt declines, potentially boosting their ROE. However, they must simultaneously maintain robust exchange rate risk management strategies, particularly if they have significant import dependencies or foreign-denominated debt, to mitigate the adverse effects of currency fluctuations.

Challenges faced by the Nigerian consumer goods sector, such as volatile input costs, supply chain disruptions, and intense competition, further emphasize the need for flexible capital structure management. Companies should strive to maintain financial flexibility by preserving unused debt capacity and maintaining cash reserves. This approach can help them weather economic downturns and take advantage of growth opportunities without resorting to excessive leverage.

Additionally, Nigerian consumer goods companies should explore alternative financing sources beyond traditional debt, such as supply chain financing, factoring, or revenue-based financing. These innovative solutions can provide the benefits of additional capital without the same level of impact on the debt-to-assets ratio, potentially enhancing their overall financial performance.

Establishing industry-wide initiatives to benchmark capital structures and financial performance can also be valuable. This would allow companies to better understand their position relative to peers and identify best practices in capital structure management, ultimately improving their decision-making processes.

Finally, enhancing investor communication strategies to explain capital structure decisions and their expected impact on financial performance can help build trust and align stakeholder expectations. This transparency can be particularly important in the Nigerian consumer goods sector, where macroeconomic volatility and intense competition require companies to demonstrate their financial agility and resilience.

In conclusion, this study offers a comprehensive understanding of the complex relationship between capital structure and financial performance in the context of Nigerian consumer goods companies. The findings highlight the need for a flexible and adaptable approach to capital structure management, one that considers both firm-specific factors and macroeconomic conditions to optimize financial performance and navigate the challenges faced by the sector.

6.2 Contribution to Knowledge

6.2.1 Theoretical Contributions

This study contributes to the existing theories on capital structure and their implications for financial performance, as measured by Return on Equity (ROE), in the context of the Nigerian consumer goods sector.

Firstly, the findings lend support to the trade-off theory by revealing the complex relationship between leverage and ROE. The significant positive interaction between debt-to-asset ratio (DTA) and inflation underscores the theory's emphasis on balancing the costs and benefits of debt financing. During inflationary periods, the real value of debt decreases, which can benefit highly

leveraged firms and improve their ROE, as observed in the study. This suggests that companies can optimize their capital structure to take advantage of the tax benefits of debt while mitigating the potential costs of financial distress.

Secondly, the study's findings contribute to the pecking order theory by highlighting the dynamic nature of financing decisions in practice. The insignificant base effects of DTA and debt-to-equity ratio (DTE) on ROE suggest that firms in the Nigerian consumer goods sector may not strictly adhere to a fixed financing hierarchy. Instead, their preferences appear to shift based on prevailing macroeconomic conditions, as evidenced by the significant moderating effects of inflation and exchange rate. This suggests that the pecking order theory's proposed financing hierarchy may need to be reevaluated to account for the influence of contextual factors on capital structure decisions.

6.2.2 Empirical Contributions

This study makes several important empirical contributions to the understanding of capital structure and its impact on financial performance in the Nigerian consumer goods sector.

Firstly, the study provides valuable context-specific evidence on the relationship between leverage and ROE, filling a gap in the literature for emerging markets. By focusing on the Nigerian consumer goods sector, the findings offer insights into how capital structure decisions may differ in industries with unique characteristics, such as the consumer goods sector's sensitivity to macroeconomic conditions and intense competition.

Secondly, the study's methodological approach, which considers both DTA and DTE as proxies for capital structure, provides a more comprehensive view of leverage and its impacts. This approach contributes to a nuanced understanding of how different leverage metrics can influence financial performance, particularly when moderated by macroeconomic factors.

6.2.3 Policy Contributions

The findings of this study have several important implications for policymakers and regulators in Nigeria, particularly in the consumer goods sector.

Firstly, the results can inform the development of regulatory guidelines for capital adequacy and debt management in the Nigerian consumer goods sector. By understanding the complex relationship between leverage, macroeconomic conditions, and financial performance, policymakers can establish more tailored and effective policies to ensure the sector's financial stability and resilience.

Secondly, the study highlights the importance of effective capital structure management in corporate governance. The findings can lead to the enhancement of governance frameworks that specifically address leverage and its impact on financial performance, ensuring that companies in the Nigerian consumer goods sector adopt prudent financing practices.

Finally, the results can inform investment policies for both institutional and retail investors, providing insights into the potential risks and returns associated with different capital structures in the consumer goods sector. This can help investors make more informed decisions and contribute to the overall development of the Nigerian capital markets.

7 LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

The specific focus of this study on listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria could stand as a limitation that can be addressed by future studies who could consider other sectors like the real

estate sector, service sector and other vital sectors in the Nigeria economy where capital structure management is crucial. Furthermore, other theories relevant to capital structure and performance can be looked into in future studies to bring a broader theoretical perspective on this subject.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS [Times New Roman, 12-point, bold, left alignment]

Optional statement to thank other contributors, assistance, or financial support.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, Davis A.O., methodology, Davis A.O. and Enyi P.E; software, Enyi P.E; validation, Enyi P.E; formal analysis, Davis A.O.; investigation, Davis A.O.; resources, Davis A.O.; data curation, Davis A.O.; writing—original draft preparation, Davis A.O.; writing—review and editing, Enyi P.E and Davis A.O.; funding acquisition, Not applicable. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: No funding was gotten for this research

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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